

Electrodeposition of Sb_2Se_3 solar cells on ceramic tiles

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the first reported synthesis of Sb_2Se_3 solar cells deposited on ceramic substrates. A novel low-temperature two-step electroplating method was introduced for fabricating high-quality Sb_2Se_3 thin films, aimed at creating efficient and reproducible solar cells. The films were deposited on Mo-coated ceramic substrates, as well as on glass substrates, addressing challenges such as high surface roughness and potential short-circuiting in ceramics. Detailed characterization of the films included X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The performance of the solar cells was evaluated through I-V curve analysis, demonstrating that ceramic substrates are a viable alternative to glass substrates. These results represent a significant advancement in integrating Sb_2Se_3 solar cells into building materials, enhancing the potential of building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) technology.

1. Introduction

The global energy economy is moving towards a shift in energy generation sources, with photovoltaic solar cells playing a key role in this transition [1,2]. Increasingly, these solar cells are being integrated into architectural designs, enabling the utilization of large surface areas in urban environments [3,4]. Despite the fact that Si solar cells are dominating the market due to economic scalability and their high-power conversion efficiency (PCE). There are other possible alternatives to this technology that have appeared in recent years, presenting themselves as possible candidates to replace or coexist with Silicon [5,6]. These include organic solar cells such as perovskites, attractive for their low price and high efficiency, although they tend to degrade quickly, tandem solar cells, which shows good efficiency and long-lasting, but with a high market price, and inorganic thin-film solar cells which, depending on the specific technology can be expensive or show a low efficiency [7].

Some mature inorganic thin-film photovoltaic (TFPV) chalcogenide absorbers such as $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})(\text{S,Se})_2$ (CIGS) and cadmium telluride (CdTe) (PCEs of 23.6 % and 22.3 %, respectively), are also used leading to an increase in their industrial deployment and module production

[7,8]. Although these technologies are achieving notable results among TFPV, they contain elements that are considered toxic (such as Cd in CdTe) or rare and expensive (such as In, Ga, or Te) which will hinder the terawatt scaling of this technology [9–11].

In this way, in the past years, some light absorber materials made by more abundant materials appeared. Despite advancements in this area, alternatives such as copper zinc tin sulfide/selenide (CZTSSe) have faced limitations, like the materials' chemical complexity, [12,13] which makes difficult to obtain efficiencies of more than 16 % affecting to their industrial profitability [7,14].

In that context, a resurgent interest in more simple chalcogenide semiconductors, with non-toxic materials appeared such as elemental Se [15], binary compounds Sb_2Se_3 , SnS [15,16], GeSe [17,18], or ternary compounds like CuSbS_2 [19,20] or Cu_2SnS_3 [21,22]. Among the previously mentioned materials studied, Sb_2Se_3 has garnered significant attention due to its promising properties that make it a very good candidate for being used in photovoltaic technologies [23]. Sb_2Se_3 exhibits direct and indirect band gaps of 1.2–1.3 eV and 1.0–1.2 eV, respectively, which are ideal for solar cell applications [24]. This advantageous band gap is complemented by an absorption coefficient of

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10^5 cm^{-1} at 1.2 eV, which, although lower than that of CIGS or CZTSe, is still highly effective for photovoltaic applications. Furthermore, it features relatively low-temperature grain growth, a stable phase, and is composed of earth-abundant, low-toxicity materials and the fact that it has a relatively long average carrier lifetime, makes the material a good candidate for photovoltaic solar cells [25]. Owing to these excellent physical properties, research on Sb_2Se_3 has intensified, with its efficiency (Eff) rapidly increasing from 0.99 % in 2011 to 10.57 % in 2022 [26].

Various methods have been explored for synthesizing Sb_2Se_3 with tailored shapes, sizes, and compositions. Among these, the most extensively studied synthesis methods include sputtering [27], hydrothermal processes [28], chemical bath deposition [29], and physical vapor deposition [30]. However, these methods are predominantly limited to laboratory-scale production. The overarching objective is to develop thin films with high reproducibility using a method that offers simplicity, scalability, and economic viability. Among all the deposition methods, electroplating deposition presents a promising solution for fabricating Sb_2Se_3 thin films efficiently and cost-effectively thanks to its rapid and reproducible deposition [31].

Another significant advantage of Sb_2Se_3 is its compatibility with a wide range of substrates due to the weak synthesis conditions, making it suitable for applications like agrovoltatics and building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV). BIPV dispositives offer a main advantage against conventional solar panels installed in solar fields, as it not only allows the generation of “kilometer 0” electricity, suffering less energy losses due to transport of it, but it also facilitates the installation of the panels during the build construction saving costs of installation and being more architecturally integrated at the same time than an average Silicon solar panels. While glass is already widely used in BIPV applications, ceramic tiles present a slightly more economical alternative. Additionally, ceramics offer higher mechanical resistance and are easier to install in building exteriors, further reducing costs. Despite the growing number of publications on Sb_2Se_3 , there is no previous report of Sb_2Se_3 solar cells being fabricated on ceramic tiles. Most studies have utilized substrates such as glass, molybdenum foils, or polyimide [32]. Although integrating this technology in ceramic substrates is a promising approach for BIPV devices, several challenges need to be addressed, such as high surface roughness and the potential for surface holes that can short-circuit the device. To prevent it, special enamels must be formulated to obtain near 0 roughness surfaces suitable for the photovoltaic solar cells dispositives (see in Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Information). Additionally, it is crucial to consider the formulation of the ceramic frit to prevent the diffusion of undesirable elements from the ceramic tile or

from the enamel into the device which would cause a decrease in the efficiency [12,33,34]. Therefore, an optimization process for conditioning the ceramic tile is necessary before its use as a substrate for photovoltaic solar cells, which would represent a significant advancement in integrating this technology into buildings [13].

As per the above statements, herein, we study the first reported synthesis of Sb_2Se_3 solar cells made on a ceramic substrate and compare the result with the glass substrates. Also, a novel low-temperature two-step electroplating method for the deposition of Sb_2Se_3 thin films is reported, which can be advantageous for its industrial implementation and scalability. In the work, we first investigate the optimal conditions for the deposition of Sb thin films in terms of deposition voltage and current. This procedure yields a homogeneous Sb metallic film, which is subsequently selenized to form the desired Sb_2Se_3 . As a result, uniform Sb_2Se_3 thin films are grown on various Mo-coated substrates.

The complete device (schematized in Fig. 1), is composed of a molybdenum film, followed by Sb_2Se_3 and CdS, ZnO, and indium-doped tin oxide (ITO) films. Molybdenum serves as the back contact in the device, playing a critical role in collecting holes generated in the absorber layer while maintaining good electrical conductivity and adhesion to the underlying substrate [35,36]. CdS and intrinsic ZnO (iZnO) films function as the electron transport layers (ETLs), facilitating the efficient extraction of electrons generated in the absorber while blocking holes to reduce recombination losses. CdS, a widely used n-type buffer layer, forms a favorable junction with Sb_2Se_3 , while iZnO improves the interface properties and aids in the alignment of energy levels, further enhancing electron transport [37–39]. Finally, ITO acts as the transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layer, allowing light to enter the device while also serving as the front contact that collects electrons from the ETLs [40]. The thickness of the ITO layer is carefully optimized to balance its transparency with electrical conductivity, ensuring minimal optical losses and efficient charge collection.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and reagents

All chemicals used for the device fabrication were of analytical grade and used directly without further purification. The following reagents were used: hydrochloric acid fuming (HCl 37 %, Supelco), potassium antimony(III) oxide tartrate trihydrate ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{K}_2\text{O}_{12}\text{Sb}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O} \geq 99 \%$, Supelco), selenium powder (Se $\geq 99 \%$, Merck), cadmium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} \geq 99 \%$, Sigma Aldrich), thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S} \geq 99 \%$, Sigma Aldrich), and ammonia solution (NH_3 25 %, PanReac).

Fig. 1. Scheme of a Sb_2Se_3 solar cell using a ceramic tile as a substrate, along with a representation of building-integrated solar cells.

2.2. Substrate adequation

The prepared ceramic tile substrates were commercial porcelanic stonewares with 5 mm of thickness. According to the industrial supplier, the tiles were fabricated using feldspar, feldspathic sand, and kaolinitic clay via the traditional ceramic industrial methodology. The final substrate composition in oxide weight (wt.%) was: 60–70 of SiO₂, 18–20 of Al₂O₃, 3.5–4.5 of Na₂O, 1.5–3 of K₂O, and other oxides with less than 1 %. As a result of the process, a low-porosity porcelain tile (>0.1 %) was manufactured, which later allowed us to work more easily in high-vacuum processes.

Previous to the deposition of the back contact with molybdenum (Mo), the porcelain was coated with an enamel film to ensure a low roughness and no porosity trying to simulate a glass surface. The frit final composition in oxide wt.% was 2 % of Na₂O, 4.6 % of K₂O, 7.3 of Al₂O₃, 8.5 % of CaO, 11.7% of ZnO, 62.3 of SiO₂ and less than 1 % of other oxides like MgO, TiO₂ and B₂O₃. The enamel was applied using a metallic applicator with a 0.3 mm opening, dried in an oven at 100 °C for 2 h, and fired at 1200 °C for 10 min following a standard porcelain firing cycle. As a conductive back contact, a 750 nm Mo trilayer film was deposited on the previously covered enameled ceramic substrate using a DC magnetron sputtering system (Alliance AC450). In both cases (for glass and for ceramic substrates) the deposition conditions used were exactly the same, for that, the first 500 nm layer was deposited at 4.2 W cm⁻² and at a pressure of 1.3·10⁻³ mbar. Then, a second layer of 250 nm was deposited at 2.8 W cm⁻² and 5·10⁻³ mbar, and finally, a 50 nm layer with the same characteristics than the first one was deposited to obtain a layer with a sheet resistance of 0.3 Ω sq⁻¹.

2.3. Device fabrication

The growth of the Sb₂Se₃ was done in two steps. In the first step, Sb films were deposited on Mo-coated glasses or ceramics. The electrolyte used was a 0.5 M potassium antimony tartrate solution made from 20 mL of 37 % concentrated hydrochloric acid and 10 mL of water.

Electrochemical experiments were carried out using a two-electrode system with a laboratory-adjustable power supply. The two-electrode configuration electrochemical cell used was a Mo-coated substrate (geometric area of 2.0 × 2.5 cm) as a working electrode and a graphite rectangle of 3.0 × 2.5 cm was used as a counter electrode. For this purpose, first, the Mo glasses were cut into 2.5 × 2.5 cm square pieces and were rinsed with ethanol, deposited in an ammonia solution, and ultrasonicated for 30 min to eliminate the molybdenum oxides. After that, the Mo-glasses were rinsed with distilled water and rapidly immersed in the electroplating solution. 310 nm Sb films were grown by applying -1.1 V to the cathode until 2 Coulombs passed (approximately 30 s).

Next, a thermal treatment with selenium powder in a tubular furnace was applied to make the Sb₂Se₃. For the treatment, the samples were placed in a graphite box between 2 lines of 20 mg selenium powder. The box was placed in a tubular furnace where 3 cycles of vacuum and N₂ were done. Subsequently, the tube was filled with N₂ gas at 0.6 atm. And the selenization was conducted with a heating ramp of 6 min up to 320 °C, where the sample was maintained 19 min and allowed to cool free. Then, a 60 nm CdS film was grown on the absorber layer. For it, the sample was immersed for 40 min in an 80 °C solution containing Cd (NO₃)₂ 0.12 M, thiourea 0.3 M, and enough NH₃ to adjust the solution to a pH value of 9.5. Later, a 50 nm zinc oxide (ZnO) layer and a 150 nm conductive indium-doped tin oxide (ITO) films were deposited using a DC pulsed sputtering (Alliance Concept T100) at 200 °C. Finally, 3 × 3 mm² solar cells were insulated using a mechanical diamond scriber MR200 OEG.

2.4. Measurements and characterization

The Sb and Sb₂Se₃ thin films were analyzed using X-ray diffraction

(XRD) in a PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD *alpha1* powder diffractometer. The instrument was equipped with a Cu tube operating at 45 kV and 40 mA, a Ge (111) Johansson type primary focalizing monochromator and a solid state strip PIXcel^{1D} detector. An automatic divergence slit system and a mask enabled a constant irradiated surface (10x12 mm²) over the analysed sample so that, considering the finite thickness of the analysed thin films, the diffracting volume is constant over all the measured angular range. High resolution, high statistics, full angular range, Cu K_{α1} (λ = 1.5406 Å) data were obtained through a 2θ/θ scan from 4 to 145° 2θ with a step size 0.013° and a measuring time per step of 200 s (PIXcel^{1D} detector: active length = 3.347°) performing three consecutive repeated scans with total measuring time 7.2 h.

The obtained XRD data enabled, as a first approximation, to evaluate the crystallinity and to identify the crystalline phases, major and minor ones, indexing the observed crystalline peaks, with the aid of the PDF#4 data base of the ICDD [41]. In a further approximation the XRD data enabled a Rietveld [42] full profile analysis. The refinements were performed using the TOPAS v6 software [43] The peak width of each phase was modelled with the Double-Voigt Approach by considering both the Lorentzian contribution of the crystallite size effect and the Gaussian contribution of the microstrain to the peak width [44] Preferential orientation corrections were applied by spherical harmonics. [45] The background was modelled with a 20th order Chebyshev polynomial. The instrumental contribution to the diffraction profile was calculated with the Fundamental Parameters Approach [46].

The Raman spectra were obtained using a single-stage dispersive spectrometer Horiba Jobin-Yvon LabRam HR 800 coupled to an optical microscope Olympus BXFM with a grating of 600 g/mm and a CCD detector cooled at -65 °C using as an excitation source a 532 nm diode-pumped solid-state laser. Some of the Raman spectra obtained with the 532 nm laser were recorded using an Ultra Low Frequency (ULF) accessory which allows the obtention of both Stokes and Anti-Stokes Raman spectra very close to the laser line (down to 10 cm⁻¹). The near infrared Raman spectrum presented here was acquired using a diode laser emitting at 785 nm with a dispersive grating of 300/mm.

The profilometry was made using a model Dektak 6 M mechanical profilometer using 5 μm linear analysis. A Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), model JEOL 7001F, fitted with an energy dispersive X-ray analyzer (EDX), was used to examine the morphology and elemental composition of the films. The layer thickness was determined from cross-sectional micrographs. The solar cells were optoelectronically characterized using I-V curves measured with a Sun 3000 class AAA solar simulator from Abet Technology, which provided a uniform illumination area of 15 × 15 cm². Measurements were conducted after calibrating the system with a reference Si solar cell under AM 1.5 illumination and setting the sample temperature to 298 K. All the solar cell parameters and efficiencies reported here refer to the active area (0.087 cm²) of the devices.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) experiments were conducted using a PHI 5500 Multitechnique System from Physical Electronics. A monochromatic Al K_α X-ray source with an energy of 1486.6 eV and a power of 350 W was employed, positioned perpendicular to the analyzer axis. Calibration was achieved using the Ag 3d_{5/2} line, which exhibited a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 0.8 eV. The analyzed area was a circular spot with a diameter of approximately 0.8 mm. For the survey spectra, which covered a binding energy range from 0 to 1100 eV, a pass energy (PE) of 187.5 eV and a step size of 0.8 eV were selected. High-resolution spectra for the primary orbitals of the elements of interest (Sb 3d, O 1 s, Se 4d, and C 1 s) were recorded with a PE of 23.5 eV and a step size of 0.1 eV. It is important to note that the O 1 s and Sb 3d_{5/2} signals overlap within the binding energy range, which should be considered during quantitative analysis. Prior to measurement, the surface was cleaned with ethanol followed by nitrogen drying. Additionally, light sputtering with Ar⁺ ions was performed inside the Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) chamber for 30 s, resulting in surface erosion of less than 10 nm. XPS spectra were analyzed and fitted using the

Multipak 9.9.08 software package from ULVAC-PHI. Binding energies were referenced to the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV, attributed to adventitious carbon from atmospheric contamination. For quantitative analysis, data from sputtered samples were used, and relative sensitivity factors corrected for the analyzer parameters and experimental geometry were applied. These factors were provided by the software. Charge compensation was not utilized in these UHV measurements, which were conducted at pressures ranging between 10^{-9} and $2 \cdot 10^{-8}$ torr.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sb and Sb₂Se₃ thin films characterization

3.1.1. Structural characterization

The main structural properties of the metallic and selenized antimony films were obtained with the first approximation evaluation of the X-ray diffraction (XRD) data and can be seen in Fig. 2a. The diffractogram of the metallic Sb film, in the main angular range from 20 to 80 °2θ, shows the diffraction peaks of the Mo layers of the back contact. Moreover, two broad XRD peaks (halos) around 30 and around 47 °2θ, indicate the presence of the amorphous (or partially crystalline or nanocrystalline) metallic Sb phase. Additional details can be found in Fig. S2 of the Supplementary Information, where plots of the diffractograms in the full angular 2θ range are presented.

Fig. 2a also depicts the diffractogram of the selenized Sb₂Se₃ thin film, in the main angular range from 20 to 80 °2θ, with the patterns of the two main identified crystalline phases superimposed, Mo from the back contact and the α-Sb₂Se₃ phase, *Antimonseleite*, orthorhombic space group *Pbnm*, the main phase in the absorber layer. In the literature, this structure is also commonly described using the *Pnma* space group notation, with the ribbons along the (001) direction which is an equivalent representation of the same crystal symmetry [47]. The crystal structure of the main phase α-Sb₂Se₃ is shown in Fig. 2(c,d) [48]. Furthermore, some additional low intensity diffraction peaks indicate the presence of some minor phases in the absorber layer, α-Sb₂O₃, *Senarmonite*, cubic *Fd3m* and β-Sb₂O₃, *Valentinite*, orthorhombic *Pccn*, and the very probable presence of a nanocrystalline (Mo,Se), e.g. Mo₁₅Se₁₉, in the underlying hole transport layer. Fig. S3 of the Supplementary Information depicts the XRD diagram with PDF patterns of all identified phases superimposed.

A further approximation Rietveld full profile analysis was performed

using the XRD data of the selenized Sb₂Se₃ thin film sample. On the one hand, the analysis results in the semi-quantification of the phases in the absorber: 98.1 % α-Sb₂Se₃, 0.6 % α-Sb₂O₃, and 1.3 % β-Sb₂O₃. On the other hand, the analysis enabled the structural, microstructural and preferred orientation analysis of the main absorber phase α-Sb₂Se₃. Results are detailed in Section 2 and figure S4 of the Supplementary Information.

The characterization of both films was further complemented by Raman spectroscopy, as shown in Fig. 3. Very low laser intensities were used to obtain the Raman spectra of the Sb film since it was observed that these layers were sensitive to laser power. This sensitivity is illustrated in Fig. 3a, where two spectra were acquired using the Ultra-Low Frequency (ULF) accessory, showing both the Raman Stokes and anti-Stokes bands at 50 μW and 500 μW, respectively. The Raman spectrum recorded at very low laser power reveals a weak broad band around -140 cm^{-1} (anti-Stokes) and $+140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Stokes), corresponding to amorphous Sb.

When the laser power is increased to more conventional values used in Raman microscopy, such as 0.5 mW, the Raman spectrum of Sb changes significantly. At the same position as the previous spectrum, new bands appear at -118 , $+118$, -150 , and $+150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to the E_g and A_{1g} vibrational modes of metallic Sb (Raman-active modes of the D_{3d} group). This indicates that the original amorphous layer has recrystallized in a microscopic region approximately matching the laser spot size, around 1 μm. Additionally, by comparing the optical micrographs in Fig. 3b, obtained before and after exposing the Sb layer to 0.5 mW laser power, a noticeable change in brightness at the laser spot is observed. This change can be correlated with the recrystallized region. These findings confirm previous studies on the low stability of amorphous Sb when subjected to thermal effects or pressure [49–51].

Fig. 3c presents the Raman spectra of Sb₂Se₃ under two different excitation lines, 532 nm (in red) and 785 nm (in green). Some spectral differences are noticeable, likely due to pre-resonance effects. According to theoretical studies, Sb₂Se₃ has 30 Raman-active modes: 10 A_g, 5 B_{1g}, 10 B_{2g}, and 5 B_{3g}. Some Sb₂Se₃ peaks can be observed in the spectrum at 80.1, 100.1, 118.7, 191.5, and 212.8 cm⁻¹ corresponding to A_g modes and one at 154.4 cm⁻¹ corresponding to a B_{xg} mode according to the literature [48,52].

Some tiny micro-crystals in the Sb₂Se₃ layer were also detected and analyzed with the Raman micro-spectrometer as indicated in Fig. S5 and were identified as minor traces of α-Sb₂O₃ (Senarmonite) confirming

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of (a) metallic and selenized (Sb₂Se₃) antimony films deposited on molybdenum. Crystal structure of α-Sb₂Se₃ phase [40]: (c) unit cell with the coordination polyhedral of Sb, (d) view along the [010] orientation highlighting the generation of ribbon-type motive.

Fig. 3. (a) Raman spectra for the Sb thin film recorded in normal (red line) and ultra-low frequency (blue line) modes. (b) Optical micrographs obtained before and after exposing the Sb film to 0.5 mW laser power. (c) Raman spectra of Sb_2Se_3 film obtained with 532 nm (in green with ULF accessory) and 785 nm (in red) excitation lines. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the XRD analysis.

3.1.2. XPS

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was also utilized to analyze the antimony and antimony selenide films, focusing on their chemical

composition and the valence states of the elements. The survey spectra, Fig. 4(a,c), reveal the presence of a C 1 s peak at the surface, which disappears after Ar^+ sputtering. This peak corresponds to adventitious carbon contamination resulting from air exposure of the samples. A high resolution of the Sb_2Se_3 film before the Ar^+ sputtering is shown in

Fig. 4. XPS analysis of the thin films. (a,b) Survey spectra of the Sb and the Sb_2Se_3 films respectively. (c,d) High resolution spectra and fittings for the $\text{Sb } 3d_{5/2}$ orbital after Ar^+ sputtering of the Sb and the Sb_2Se_3 films, respectively.

Fig. S6 revealing the presence of some Sb_2O_3 . Some High-resolution spectra were also taken after Ar^+ sputtering, Fig. 4(b,d), indicate that only metallic antimony (Sb^0) bonds are present in the antimony film. In contrast, the antimony selenide film after the Ar^+ sputtering exhibits two distinct peaks: one at higher binding energies corresponding to Sb^{3+} (representing 94 % of the total peak, linked to selenium) and a smaller peak corresponding to Sb^0 (6 % of the total peak, indicating metallic antimony). The calculated atomic percentages of selenium and antimony in the film were 55 % and 45 %, respectively. After accounting for the small amount of metallic antimony, the effective Sb/Se ratio in the antimony selenide film is 0.77. This suggests that the film is Sb-rich, which, according to the literature, is considered less optimal for photovoltaic solar cells compared to Se-rich films [25].

3.1.3. Morphological characterization

Fig. 5 illustrates the morphological transformation of an Sb film before and after selenization. In Fig. 5a, a cross-sectional view of the antimony film, electrodeposited onto a Mo substrate, is shown. The film appears remarkably homogeneous and continuous, with a uniform thickness, indicating a well-controlled deposition process. Such homogeneity is crucial for ensuring consistent and predictable behavior in subsequent processing steps, as it minimizes the likelihood of defects that could compromise the film's electronic and structural properties.

Fig. 5b depicts the film after undergoing selenization. The transformation from Sb to Sb_2Se_3 is accompanied by significant morphological changes. Notably, the formation of well-defined grains is observed, with grain sizes comparable to the overall film thickness. The emergence of large, columnar grains suggests that the crystal growth occurs perpendicular to the substrate, which is often desirable for enhancing charge carrier transport in thin-film solar cells. The continuity of the film post-selenization, combined with the presence of these grains, points to a successful phase transition from amorphous or nanocrystalline Sb to crystalline Sb_2Se_3 .

3.2. Solar cell characterization

3.2.1. Morphological characterization

Fig. 5c presents a cross-sectional image of the complete device structure. At the base of the image, the enamel layer of the ceramic tile is visible. This enamel serves as a protective barrier, isolating the ceramic substrate from the functional layers of the solar cell. The use of ceramic tiles as substrates in building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) highlights the integration of solar energy harvesting directly into construction materials, where the enamel layer ensures chemical stability and adhesion for the subsequent layers.

Above the enamel, a molybdenum (Mo) film can be observed, with an average thickness of approximately 750 nm. Next, a 550 nm thick Sb_2Se_3 film, which functions as the absorber layer, is visible. The Sb_2Se_3 layer exhibits columnar grains with heights corresponding to the thickness of the film, as previously appreciated in Fig. 5b. On top of the Sb_2Se_3 absorber layer, thin films of CdS and intrinsic ZnO (iZnO), each about 50 nm thick, are observed. At the top of the device, a 150 nm thick indium tin oxide (ITO) film is present, which acts as the transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layer.

3.2.2. Solar cell performance

Fig. 6a shows the illuminated J-V curves for the best Sb_2Se_3 solar cell results obtained on glass and ceramic substrates. In addition, Table 1 presents the most relevant parameters of the J-V analysis for these samples. The amperage results obtained are satisfactory; however, the V_{oc} is lower compared to other studies in the literature, ultimately impacting the fill factor (FF). This behavior may be attributed to the presence of oxides detected in the analysis and could also result from an Sb-rich film, as discussed in the previous section. Despite some improvements could be done to improve the efficiency of the dispositives, this study is focused on the viability of the use of ceramic tiles as a

Fig. 5. SEM cross-section micrographs: (a) as deposited Sb thin film, (b) Sb_2Se_3 thin film after the selenization treatment, (c) completed solar cell on ceramic tile.

substrate for photovoltaic solar cells. In that sense, a comparative histogram between all efficiencies obtained for glass and for ceramic tiles substrates was made (Fig. 6b and Fig. 6c respectively). It can be observed that in both cases the substrates are suitable for being used in solar cells, despite this, the ceramic tile seems to have less dispersion in the results obtaining a similar average efficiency in both cases, which

Fig. 6. (a) I-V curves for the best Sb_2Se_3 solar cells deposited on glass and ceramic substrates and (b,c) all the obtained efficiencies for each substrate.

Table 1

Solar cells I-V parameters for the devices of Fig. 6a.

Sample	Jsc (mA/cm^2)	Voc (mV)	FF%	Eff %
Glass	29.09	237	34.60	2.38
Ceramic	28.93	245	30.04	2.13

would demonstrate the viability of the use of ceramic tiles for Sb_2Se_3 solar cells.

4. Conclusion

This study presents the first reported synthesis of Sb_2Se_3 solar cells on ceramic substrates, demonstrating that ceramic tiles can serve as viable alternatives to glass substrates for photovoltaic applications. The developed low-temperature two-step electroplating method successfully produced uniform and high-quality Sb_2Se_3 thin films. The precursor antimony film was deposited in only 30 s followed by a thermal treatment at 320 °C for 20 min making the process fast and highly reproducible in the industry. Despite initial challenges related to substrate surface roughness and potential short circuits, the optimized ceramic substrates showed promising results. Characterization techniques confirmed the films' structural integrity and composition, and efficiencies of 2.38 % and 2.13 % were obtained on glass and ceramic tiles. The solar cells fabricated on ceramic tiles exhibited comparable efficiency to those on glass substrates, highlighting the potential for integrating Sb_2Se_3 -based solar cells into building materials, thereby enhancing the applicability of BIPV systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Samuel Porcar: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Abderrahim Lahlahi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jaime González Cuadra:** Visualization, Supervision, Data curation. **Santiago Toca:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Pablo Serna-Gallén:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Data curation. **Diego Fraga:** Supervision. **Tariq Jawhari:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Xavier Alcobe:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lorenzo Calvo Barrio:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pedro Vidal-Fuentes:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Alejandro Pérez-Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Juan Bautista Carda:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal

relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Samuel Porcar Garcia reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science and Innovation. Samuel Porcar reports financial support was provided by State Agency of Research. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2025.113377>.

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